

№ 2

27.05.2023

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

@ferteach_uz

+99893-343-13-14

<https://fer-teach.uz>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. PhD., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.B.Mallabayev - tarix f.n., dotsent. NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

X.K.Boymirzayev - ped. f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

I.U.Kuzikulov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

B.T.Mirzadjanov - tarix f.b. PhD, , NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

M.A.Maxmudov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МЫШЛЕНИЯ МЛАДШЕГО КЛАССА

Холдарова Иродахон Валиджоновна

Доктор философии филологических наук (PhD)

Абдуолимова Мархабо Илхомжон кызы

ФарДУ, аспирант 2 курса

Аннотация: В данной статье учитель должен с первого дня занятий заинтересовать учащихся начальных классов всесторонними знаниями по предметам, изучить психическое состояние ребенка, как заинтересовать детей в процессе урока. А также, как провести простой урок письма ученику, как правильно сидеть за партой, правильно держать ручку, класть тетрадь по правилам, соблюдать дистанцию между глазами и тетрадью. , проанализированы мнения о способах достижения красивой личности.

Ключевые слова: Почерк, соревнование, игры, умственное напряжение, педагогические технологии, интеллектуальное развитие.

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS CHILDREN

Xoldarova Irodakhon Valijonovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Philological Sciences (PhD)

Abduolimova Markhabo Ilkhomjon kizi

FarDU, 2nd year graduate student

Abstract: In this article, the teacher should start from the first day of school to interest primary school students in comprehensive knowledge of subjects, study the mental state of the child, and how to interest children in the lesson process. Also, how to teach a simple writing lesson to a student, how to sit correctly at the desk, hold the pen correctly, put the notebook according to the rules, keep the distance between the eyes and the notebook By explaining such aspects to the students, opinions on ways to achieve a beautiful personality were analyzed.

Keywords: Hand writing, competition, games, mental stress, pedagogical technologies, intellectual development.

Introduction. It is known that a child who steps on the threshold of school for the first time goes through the preparatory period before school. In this period, his pedagogical and psychological preparation for the center of knowledge is of

great importance. Because from this period, the child's imagination and attitude towards school will be fully formed. We can't say that all students who step onto the platform of knowledge come directly from preparatory groups. Some of them are accepted from preparatory classes opened at school, some from special groups in kindergarten, and some are admitted to the first grade without any preparation. No matter how the child arrives, his attitude towards school, studies and the teacher should be positive. The role of parents is especially important here. Here, our child has been accepted to school. The daily environment in his life changes. It should not be forgotten that the interaction between the first teacher and the parents who accepted the student plays a very important role in the student's easy adaptation to school activities. Just like the joint care of a father and a mother for the development of a child, now a third party teacher begins to influence his education and upbringing. Therefore, the demand placed on the child and the influence of both sides on its fulfillment should be the same and mutually compatible. A mentally and physically healthy child does not become a poorly educated or lazy student. Even if this is the case, parents or teachers are more likely to cause it. If the student is not learning from the lessons, the teacher should first determine the reason and use the most useful method. For this, using the following is effective:

1. Speaking well and praising.
2. To set a positive example for others.
3. Greater involvement in organizational work.
4. Giving more importance to teaching on the basis of interdisciplinary communication [1]. These reasons increase students' activity in class.

Main body

The teacher should start from the first day of school to interest the student in learning all kinds of subjects. For example, if we take a simple writing lesson, by explaining how to sit correctly at the desk, hold the pen correctly, put the notebook according to the rules, and keep the distance between the eyes and the notebook, their manners are beautiful. and at the same time it is said that it is important for health. It is even explained through pictures that if the above rules are not followed, vision impairment and spinal curvature may occur. Other classes are conducted in the same way. The special features of each subject should be explained, and it should be fully conveyed to the child's mind that the subjects taught in the upper grades are interconnected and integrally connected with the current lessons. In primary grades, basic subjects are taught by only one teacher and it is based on the following goals:

1. Educating well-educated young people who can think independently.
2. To increase the child's interest in obtaining excellent knowledge in the subject he loves, according to his independent direction [2].

Competitions, games and various puzzles are good for making the lesson more active and interesting for students, especially elementary school students[3].

However, it is necessary not to deviate from the main purpose of the lesson, to pay attention to the fact that games and puzzles are based on the subject of the lesson. It is his greatest achievement if the teacher is able to prepare visual aids and handouts that are relevant not only to one subject, but to several subjects, even to several classes. The use of cards, test tasks, puzzles, various games in the lesson also gives the expected effect in all respects. The use of interesting games that encourage activity and sharpen the mind in classes ensures the normal growth of the student both physically and mentally.

The junior school period starts from 6-7 years old and lasts until 9-10 years old. During this period, the child gets acquainted with various requirements for schoolchildren, is biologically and psychologically prepared to learn the basics of science. His psyche develops enough to acquire knowledge. A child of this age is distinguished from children of other ages by his sharpness of perception, clarity, purity, accuracy, curiosity, trustworthiness, brightness of imagination, strength of memory, clarity of thinking. In a child preparing for school education, attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable [4]. The main activity of children of primary school age is reading. A child's going to school is extremely important for his psychological development and personality formation. Under the guidance of the teacher, the child learns the content of various basic forms of human consciousness and learns to act on the basis of human traditions.

In educational activities, the child exercises his will to achieve educational goals. Educational activities require the child to develop speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking to the required level, and create new conditions for the development of the child's personality. A child who comes to school for the first time enters a new system of psychological relationships with others. He begins to feel that his life has changed radically, that he has new obligations not only to go to school every day, but also to obey the demands of academic activities. The fact that the family members are interested in the child's educational activities and achievements, as well as the fact that they control him, the new forms of treatment given to him are the basis for his full feeling that his social status has changed, and for the change of his attitude towards himself. [5]. Adults teach children to study, play, go for a walk and do other things. So, in the family, the child occupies a new place where he can be counted and consulted.

A student's success at school is a completely positive basis for his further mental development and personality formation. A child occupies a special place in the system of human relations, parents, relatives, and others are not like a young child to him. rather, they are treated as a separate person who has duties and obligations and can be respected according to the results of their activities. As a result, it can be seen that the child begins to understand his place in his family, class and other communities. During this period, the motive of the child "I want this" and "I must do this" begins to prevail. Mental stress increases in every student who enters the first grade at school [6]. This is manifested not only in his

physical health, but also in his behavior, i.e., to a certain extent, in the increase of fear and the decrease of volitional activity. By this time, the child has achieved certain results in interaction with others, knows exactly what he wants and his place in his family. He will also have self-management skills and will be able to work according to the situation and situation.

Children at this age begin to understand that their behavior and motivations are not judged by self-evaluations of “I'm a good child”, but by how these behaviors appear in the eyes of others. A child is prepared for school education while being educated in kindergarten. In psychological studies, 6-7-year-old children were asked to estimate the amount of water in containers of different heights, and the children learned that their answers were incorrect only after they saw the amount of water in containers of equal height. During the junior school period, imagination develops mainly when children draw pictures, as well as weave fairy tales and stories. The imagination of children of junior school age is very wide and diverse. Some students mainly imagine real existence, while others imagine fantastic images and situations. In this regard, children of primary school age can be divided into realists and fantasists. Children often imagine and create new images using familiar images and plots. These imaginations are based on their feelings of overcoming fear, finding friends, and happiness. In addition, imagination can be manifested as an activity that brings therapeutic results. When a child faces difficulties in real life and cannot get out of them, he often gives in to fantasy. For example, a child being brought up in an orphanage imagines that he will have a family, a house that everyone will envy, and that he will be a hero if thieves come to this house. Imagination allows the child to temporarily relax and, during this relaxation, to gather strength to continue living without parents. A nervous mother who constantly screams at her child may imagine her child as a loving angel, as a hero saving her mother from a great, terrifying danger, or as a dying mother for constantly hurting her child.

A child who experiences good or bad situations in his imagination prepares the motivation for his future behavior. Imagination is very important in children's lives compared to adults. By imagining, the child begins to know the surrounding life more deeply, he can deviate from his own personal experience with the help of imagination, his creative ability develops, and it serves the development of his personal characteristics. A child of elementary school age has a strong emotional bond with his teacher. Until this time, he has been learning this or that information directly under the guidance of adults, but now he is trying to collect the necessary information on his own will, to set a clear goal and task for himself, to research his interests perfectly. does. This activity of the child indicates the development of memory at a certain level[7]. A rationally organized educational process rapidly develops the thinking of children of this age. A child of this age learns more than at other times. School education changes the student's lifestyle, social status, the situation in the class group and family environment, and his task is to

acquire knowledge, acquire skills and abilities, and master them. One of the important characteristics of a child of primary school age is the presence of specific needs. In essence, these needs are not aimed at acquiring certain knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also reflect the desire to learn. Based on these needs, there is a desire to go to school every day as an adult, to have a diary, a lesson preparation corner for personal educational materials, and a bookshelf.

A child of primary school age does not understand his basic nature and mission, but understands that everyone should go to school. But he follows the instructions of adults and diligently starts training. After some time, as the impression of joyful moments diminishes, the external signs of school lose their importance, and the child realizes that studying is a daily mental work. Then, if the child does not have the skills of intellectual work, he will be discouraged from studying, and he will feel hopeless. And in order to prevent such a situation, the teacher should inform the child about the difference between education and play, the fun, and prepare him for this activity. The content of education is inextricably linked with the student's interest in acquiring knowledge and the feeling of satisfaction from the result of his mental work [8]. This feeling is carried out by the teacher's encouragement and forms the desire and enthusiasm of the student to work more effectively. Feelings of pride and self-confidence in the child serve to acquire knowledge and develop skills. The process of teaching children of primary school age begins with the introduction of the main components of educational activities to learning situations, learning activities, control and evaluation (according to V.V. Davidov). In this regard, it is very important that all subject activities are carried out in conditions conducive to mental development. If the child performs the learning activities incorrectly, it may be because he does not know the activities related to control and evaluation of the learning activities, or he does not master them well [9].

Conclusion

In short, the ability of a child to compare the results of actions performed independently with the characteristics of his own behavior indicates that he has developed self-control characteristics to a certain extent. as soon as they acquire them, they use them practically to solve specific problems.

References

1. Dadakhon, T., & Sabohat, A. (2022). Developing Creative Thinking through Primary School Students Solving Problems. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 6, 71-76.
2. Dadakhon, T. (2022). Factors that Review Students' Imagination in the Educational Process. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 551-557.
3. Zokirov, S., & Rakhmatova, G. (2023). The use of computer games in modern education: problems and solutions. *Engineering Problems and*

- Innovations, 1(1), 27–34. Retrieved from <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/epai/article/view/19>
4. Farkhodovich, T. D. (2022). The Problem of Forming Interpersonal Tolerance in Future Teachers. *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology*, 2(4), 12-15.
 5. Tukhtasinov, D. (2018). Development of logical thinking of pupils of 5-9th grades in the lessons of mathematics. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 209(22), 586-587.
 6. Khusanova M. K. Analysis of discrete convolution in the matlab program //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 1023-1028.
 7. Khusanova M. K. Comparison of filters with finite pulse characteristics and infinite pulse characteristics in MATLAB //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 292-299.
 8. Khusanova M. K. Using decimation and interpolation when processing signals in MATLAB //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 300-306.
 9. Хусанова М.К. Сетевая безопасность и мониторинг //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 177-183.